

NOVASOIL

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

Grant agreement ID: 101091268

Preliminary version of the knowledge hub for soil health business models

Deliverable D 3.2

Project	NOVASOIL
Project title	INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH
Work Package	3 Testing and development of a toolbox for incentives
Deliverable	3.2
Period covered	01/11/2022-31/10/2023
Publication date	31/10/2023
Dissemination level	PU
Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this report	New Bulgarian University
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QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCEDURES

This document has been reviewed by the NOVASOIL consortium according to the national reports and comments received.

TABLE REVISION HISTORY DELIVERABLE

Row	Version	Date	Reviewers	Description
1	V1.0	26/10/2023	NBU	Draft version circulated by email
2	V2.0	27/10/2023	EVENOR	Draft version circulated by email
3	V3.0	30/10/2023	NBU	Draft version circulated by email

Project Consortium

N°	Participant organisation name	Country
1	EVENOR TECH SLU	ES
2	LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG	GE
3	ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA	LV
4	NEW BULGARIAN UNIVERSITY	BU
5	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
6	KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	DK
7	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	GE
8	ASSEMBLEE DES REGIONS EUROPEENNES FRUITIERES LEGUMIERES ET HORTICOLES	FR
9	ISTITUTO DELTA ECOLOGIA APPLICATA SRL	IT
10	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	IT
11	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	NL
12	CENTRE OF ESTONIAN RURAL RESEARCH AND KNOWLEDGEEESTI	EE
13	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	ES
14	UNIVERSITA DI PISA	IT
15	ASOCIACION AGRARIA JOVENES AGRICULTORES DE SEVILLA	ES
16	UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	GB

Table of contents

List of figures	7
List of tables	7
List of abbreviations	8
Summary	9
1 Introduction	9
1.1 Context of WP 3 objectives.....	9
1.2 Connection with the other WPs	10
1.3 Purpose and scope of the document.....	10
1.4 Process of development	10
2 Conceptual framework.....	12
2.1 DHK framework.....	12
2.1.1. Internal sources of information.....	13
2.1.2. External sources of information	14
2.2 DHK features determination.....	14
2.2.1 Dynamic module	15
2.2.2 Soil health product module	15
2.2.3 Publishing module	15
2.2.4 Communication module.....	15
3. Design of the hub.....	16
3.1 Home page.....	17
3.2 About.....	20
3.2.1 Partners	21
3.2.2 Frequently Asked Questions.....	21
3.2.3 Contact us	22
3.3 Soil health business models	22
3.4 Soil health practices	22
3.5 Soil health policies.....	23
3.6 Soil health projects	23
3.7 Forum	23
3.7 Log in area.....	24
4 Conclusions.....	25
Resources	26
Acknowledgment.....	27
Annexes	28

Annex 1.....	28
Annex 2.....	31
Annex 3.....	32

List of figures

Figure 1. Knowledge exchange on the NOVASOIL DHK.....	13
Figure 2. HOVASOIL DHK architecture.....	16
Figure 3. NOVASOIL DHK home page.....	17
Figure 4. NOVASOIL DHK short description.....	18
Figure 5. NOVASOIL project presentation	18
Figure 6. NOVASOIL DHK partners	19
Figure 7. DHK latest news.....	19
Figure 8. Contact form on NOVASOIL DHK home page	20
Figure 9. NOVASOIL DHK footnote	20
Figure 10. NOVASOIL DHK About us page	21
Figure 11. NOVASOIL DHK message form	22
Figure 12. NOVASOIL DHK Forum page.....	23
Figure 13. Log in page	24

List of tables

Table 1. Form for information collection.....	13
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Summary

This document reports on a preliminary digital version on digital hub of knowledge (DHK) and an overall update on its progress carried out under T 3.2: Identification of new incentives soil health business models” in the framework of WP3 "Testing and development of a toolbox for incentives" under the NOVASOIL project.

Task 3.2 will build DHK, surveying, structuring, and connecting existing knowledge of existing incentives regarding investment opportunities at farm level of implementing different soil health business models. Additionally, DHK will ensure connection of the existing and new knowledge regarding incentives for redirection of financial streams and policy support measures for provision of innovative soil health technologies for producing safe food. The process will be fully supported by NOVASOIL partners feeding with information the DHK.

The report presents structure and modules contained in the DHK. Also, it is presented the applied user-friendly architecture of the NOVASOIL DHK and its design.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context of WP 3 objectives

The objective of the task T 3.2: Identification of new incentives soil health business models is to investigate the opportunities and gaps of new incentives and to build a DHK.

DHK will support facilities that help farmers and companies to become more competitive through the implementation of soil health business models (SHBM). The DHK acts as a one-stop-shop, providing their users with:

- Regulatory Framework,
- SHBM knowledge and competence,
- Training to develop SHBM,
- Investment opportunities,
- Soil health incentives

The DHK is developed as a web-based digital tool. The new soil health business models could significantly reduce the farmers' investment cost which will allow them to be more innovative and to provide novel opportunities for developing and diversifying their incomes.

1.2 Connection with the other WPs

Connection with WP 1 and WP2: The empirical results of WP 1 and WP 2 will be fed in DHK under WP3. Additionally, information will be provided based on the lessons learned from the key actors and stakeholders.

Connection with WP4: In the DHK will implement the obtained results for the new soil health new policies (WP 4).

Connection with WP5: Under Task 5.2 the project partners will contribute to the DHK. Moreover, essential part of this part of the T 3.2 will be shared with the audience, including the Communities of Practice in cooperation with WP 5.

1.3 Purpose and scope of the document

The deliverable D 3.2 Preliminary version of the knowledge hub for soil health business models aims to define the NOVASOIL health digital knowledge hub, which is part of Task 3.2 “Identification of new incentives soil health business models”. It is presented as a preliminary framework of DHK.

1.4 Process of development

The overall process of development of the DHK included several steps: analysis of already existing hubs or platforms, discussion with NOVASOIL partners regarding core elements of the hub, discussion and drafting of the structure, selection of service providers, development of graphic design and page title, preliminary digital version of the DHK.

The first step of the development process was a comparative analysis of existing platforms or hubs, particularly their objectives, targets, elements, and structure. It was found that no other DHK for SHBM. Despite of this, it was made an investigation about similar tools. The tools are divided into two groups: EU hubs and hubs with origin outside EU.

- EU hubs
 - The European Agroecology Exchange Hub is a virtual place and platform has been created by the University of Gastronomic Sciences, Pollenzo, Italy (UNISG), in collaboration with Zetabi for technical development, within the H2020 AE4EU project. It is a virtual space to connect all actors interested or involved in agroecology. Indeed, the hub’s vision is to develop a European network on agroecology. Encouraging networking and exchange of information, the finalities of the hub are to connect

digitally with colleagues and experts, share knowledge, insights, and best practice, learn from experiences and inspire innovation and new ways of working in Agroecology. AE4EU - <https://www.ae4eu.eu/about-ae4eu/>

- The Hub of the BOND project¹ which is focused on environmental and economic sustainability of the farming sector in Europe. The hub does not provide the opportunity for two-way knowledge exchange with the users. Website: <https://www.bondproject.eu/>
 - EURAKNOS hub is a product of EU financed project, which is sister project of EUREKA. The hub ensures the first working version of so-called “EU FarmBook” providing an open-source e-platform for collecting and sharing the many different types of end-user material produced by Horizon 2020 multi-actor projects. Website: <https://euraknos.eu/>
 - LifeWatch ERIC is a European Research Infrastructure Consortium providing e-Science research facilities to scientists investigating biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services in order to support society in addressing key planetary challenges. Their knowledge hub Virtual Research Environment provides learning materials, podcasts, and databases. Website: <https://www.lifewatch.eu/>
- Hubs outside EU
 - Agro ecological Knowledge Hub (AKH), The UNISECO project Agro-ecological Knowledge Hub is integrated into the project website. The Hub was launched in November 2018, accessible at <https://uniseco-project.eu/>. <https://uniseco-project.eu/>.
 - The AgroEcology Hub, based in Virginia, USA, facilitates lifelong learning relating to food systems, agriculture, and natural resources conservation. Website: <https://www.agroecologyhub.info/>
 - Agroecology Hub contains information about the soil health, biofertilizers, and biopesticides. The hub is focused on the soil health in Africa. Website: <https://agroecologyhub.org/>
 - GLFX is a platform for resilient landscape management. The Global Landscapes Forum (GLF) is the world's largest knowledge-led platform on sustainable and inclusive landscapes. Website: <https://www.globallandscapesforum.org/>
 - US-based Farmers Business Network (FBN) is a digital agriculture platform that connects farmers, provides them with data based solutions and offers a knowledge sharing community. It offers tools and services that help farmers make informed decisions about their operations, including agronomic analytics, market intelligence and purchasing capabilities. Website: <https://www.fbn.com/>
-

- Agroecology Knowledge Hub is managed by the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) of the United Nations. Website: <https://www.fao.org/agroecology/home/en/>

Analysis of the knowledge hubs leads to the following conclusions:

- Most of the hubs are not ensuring communication with the end users.
- Most of the hubs are not fully fed with information.
- There is no hub fully dedicated to soil health taking into consideration the resilience of the farmers in terms of business model.

In order to identify the core elements of the DHK, several meetings were organised in 2023 to co-design the hub. Those internal meetings allowed to discuss and define different categories for the future DHK.

The first discussion was organized during the First plenary project meeting in Seville, Spain (22nd and 23rd May 2023). The focus was on the main DHK functionalities. The prepared presentation for the event related to the hub is provided in Annex 1.

Then, it was organized a technical meeting between WP1 and WP3 teams (30th August 2023). There were discussed some main aspects such as main points in the design, relation with other partners, and potential collaborations with sister projects. Minutes of the meeting is presented in Annex 2.

The second discussion with all partners was held during the Second plenary project meeting in Munich, Germany (23rd and 24th October 2023). During this meeting it was defined the menu and the structure of the knowledge hub, confirmed by all partners. In addition, it was defined the process how all partners will provide information to feed up the DHK. The presentation is presented in Annex 3.

Preliminary digital version of the DHK can be found on: <https://novasoil.agma.studio/>.

2 Conceptual framework

2.1 DHK framework

The goal of DHK is to led farmers to enhance their products and services through the inclusion of knowledge exchange of existing incentives regarding investment opportunities (fig. 1). The DHK will get the opportunities to do a focused knowledge exchange application in order to implement soil health practices and solutions in the frame of SHBM. This creates a win-win situation for all stakeholders participated at the SHBM.

Figure 1. Knowledge exchange on the NOVASOIL DHK

2.1.1. Internal sources of information

To ensure the smooth information collection process within the project, it will be used the form presented in table 1. The table shows a list of Bulgarian incentives that will be uploaded on DHK as an example how each NOVASOIL partner should submit information.

Table 1. Form for information collection

Nº	Name	Short description	Link	Category on the hub	Language	Status Public/ Non-public
1	National Program for Traditional and Regional Products 2022 - 2032	The document presents several key measures for the potential of local and regional products in increasing local economy and local communities. The measures in this program are mostly knowledge-based and aiming at increasing awareness through information. Also, increasing the link between local agro-products and the touristic industry is targeted as a measure in this program.	pdf	Soil Health Policies	Bulgarian	Public
2	CAP Strategic Plan in BG 2023-2027	Main strategic document of the EU in support of agricultural development, whose main aim is to support farmers and to ensure Europe's food security.	pdf	Soil Health Policies	Bulgarian	Public
3	Agriculture as part of the EU Recovery and Resilience	A short guiding document from the Ministry of Agriculture in BG on what are the main mechanisms for encouraging environmental transition of agriculture. Contains different opportunities for investing in new environmental measures and technologies.	pdf	Soil Health Practices	Bulgarian	Public

Nº	Name	Short description	Link	Category on the hub	Language	Status Public/ Non-public
4	Practical guideline for implementing GAEC in BG 2023	A short guiding document from the Ministry of Agriculture in BG regarding several main standards in keeping the agricultural land in good ecological condition. This guideline is also implemented in the CAP Strategic plan 2023-2027. Most of the standards are directed towards improving soil health.	pdf	Soil Health Practices	Bulgarian	Public
5	EU Soil Strategy for 2030	EU strategic document on achieving good soil health, containing medium-term objectives by 2030 and long-term objectives by 2050. The document provides a good explanation on healthy soil. A connection is made between soil health and other strategic topics like circular economy, zero pollution, climate adaptations, etc.	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021DC0699	Soil Health Practices	Bulgarian	Public

2.1.2. External sources of information

The DHK content will contain information from external sources. It will be collected information from sister projects. In addition, it will be made an attempt for a meeting with DG AGRI policy officer, the Soil Mission team, and other joint sessions with other projects to discuss opportunities for cooperation (share content, cross-reference, etc.) and future avoidance of development of other knowledge hubs. A potential connection would be with the Collaborative platform from SoilValues project and other platforms. Moreover, the hub would be interfacing with LUCAS, EJP-SOIL, and EEA.

Important step will be to present the hub to the NOVASOIL project's stakeholders and to collect feedback to improve the NOVASOIL hub before the final report related to the hub - D 3.5 Report on final version of the knowledge hub for soil health business models.

2.2 DHK features determination

To define the content of soil health knowledge hub, it was applied module-based approach.

The aim is defining all the needed features that will be available and to boost the user experience. The latter is very important to attract more users and make the hub a preferable place for interaction and source of information related to the soil health. The different modules explain different dimensions of the knowledge hub. The DHK is one-level structure digital tool which combines four module knowledge exchange with additional information

about the particular soil health incentives, and connections of another knowledge for SHBM.

2.2.1 Dynamic module

This module defines the dynamic relation between two published pages. The NOVASOIL DHK will use this kind of module on different pages such as the home page for the latest news and for the hottest topics in forum.

On each page the user can access the contact form, the log-in page, and the opportunity to sign up for the newsletter.

2.2.2 Soil health product module

The product module is focused on the added value of the hub. The scope of the knowledge hub is as follows:

- To discover and explain new investment opportunities related to the soil health.
- To present and explain the soil health legislation framework.
- To focus the stakeholder attention on the appropriate incentives that could support the soil health activities.

2.2.3 Publishing module

All the features and collected information will be presented sorted by topics:

- Soil health business models;
- Soil health practices;
- Soil health policies;
- Soil health projects.

Each main topic will be developed also on a country basis in submenus/ related pages.

The main language of the knowledge hub will be English. Anyway, there will be publications in the NOVASOIL partners' national languages supported by the short description in English.

2.2.4 Communication module

This module ensures that the communication between all stakeholders will be as easy as possible.

There are navigation bars in the header and in the final part of the site (main menu and footer).

To ensure the communication with the NOVASOIL social media, it is provided social sharing buttons – Tweeter (X), LinkedIn, Facebook.

In addition, there is a form for inquiry and feedback: Name, e-mail, Telephone, Subject, Country, Massage, tick for consent to GDPR. The answers to the questions will be supported in all the NOVASOIL partners' languages.

Information pages (success/ failure) after sending the request will be available.

In addition, newsletter will be sent to the users that sign up for it.

3. Design of the hub

The NOVASOIL hub will be focused on the following topics:

- Soil health business models;
- Soil health practices;
- Soil health policies;
- Soil health projects.

On the hub, the users will be able to find videos, files, news, short stories related to these topics. The forum will be crucial ensuring the knowledge exchange between partners, stakeholders, and other users.

The architecture of the demo version of the DHK has the structure presented on figure 2.

Figure 2. NOVASOIL DHK architecture

3.1 Home page

The home page opens when the user writes or click on the DHK link. Also, the home page is opening when the user clicks on the NOVASOIL logo on the left-up corner of the page.

The first thing that the user sees is the name of the DNH – NOVASOIL KNOWLEDGE HUB – and short description of it (fig. 3). Right below that is a button related to the Forum.

Figure 3. NOVASOIL DHK home page

On this page the user could find information about the DHK, what the hub provides (fig. 4), short description of and link to the NOVASOIL project page (fig. 5), the NOVASOIL project partners logos (fig. 6), the latest news (fig. 7), contact form (fig. 8). The footnote on each page contains newsletter sign-up, links to the main menu, and contact information (fig. 9). Here it could be seen the tools of the dynamic module – the home page’s direct links to the partners, news, and contact pages.

WHO WE ARE

At Novasol hub, we are a passionate and dedicated online community that aims to connect individuals involved in agriculture and provide them with a platform to share their knowledge, experiences, and ideas.

Our community is composed of farmers, horticulturists, agronomists, and enthusiasts who are committed to sustainable and environmentally-friendly farming practices.

Join Novasol hub today and become part of a community that is passionate about agriculture, sustainability, and cultivating a better future for our planet.

Comprehensive Knowledge Base

Our platform provides users with access to a comprehensive knowledge base that includes information on crop cultivation, soil health, pest management, organic farming, and much more.

Expert Advice and Support

We understand that agriculture can present unique challenges and complexities. That's why Novasol hub provides a platform where users can seek advice and support from experts in the field.

Interactive Forums and Discussions

Our platform provides users with access to a comprehensive knowledge base that includes information on crop cultivation, soil health, pest management, organic farming, and much more.

Figure 4. NOVASOIL DHK short description

Figure 5. NOVASOIL project presentation

Our Partners

At Novasol hub, we believe in the power of collaboration and strong partnerships. We are proud to work with a diverse range of organizations and individuals who share our passion for agriculture, sustainability, and community.

Our partners play a vital role in helping us achieve our mission of building a thriving agro community and forum. Together, we collaborate on various initiatives, share resources, and leverage each other's expertise to create a positive and meaningful impact in the agricultural industry.

Figure 6. NOVASOIL DHK partners

Latest news

We invite you to join us on this journey towards a future where soil health is of paramount importance. Follow Novasol hub for the latest updates on our research, partnerships, and Initiatives, and discover how innovative business models can pave the way for a more sustainable and resilient world.

Figure 7. DHK latest news

Contact Us

Have a question, comment, or inquiry? We would love to hear from you! Send us a message using the form below, and our team will get back to you as soon as possible.

NAME	COUNTRY
<input type="text" value="Name"/>	<input type="text" value="Afghanistan"/>
PHONE	EMAIL
<input type="text" value="Phone"/>	<input type="text" value="Email"/>
SUBJECT	
<input type="text" value="Subject"/>	
MESSAGE	
<input type="text" value="Message"/>	
<input type="button" value="Send Message"/>	

Figure 8. Contact form on NOVASOIL DHK home page

Newsletter

Signup our newsletter to get update information, news, insight or promotions.

<input type="text" value="Name"/>	<input type="text" value="Email"/>
<input type="button" value="Sign up"/>	

LINKS

- About
- Soil Health Business Model
- Soil Health Practices
- Soil Health Policies
- Soil Health Projects
- Forum
- Login

GET IN TOUCH

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Funded by the European Union. Grant agreement ID: 101091268

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Figure 9. NOVASOIL DHK footnote

3.2 About

The About page aims to present the hub idea and its focus (fig. 10). Also, all the people that are involved in DHK creation, maintenance, and management. It includes information about the NOVASOIL DHK, our values, and partners.

ABOUT US

The NOVASOIL knowledge hub is for surveying, structuring and providing recommendations for connecting existing and new knowledge regarding incentives for redirection of financial streams and policy support measures for provisioning of innovative soil health technologies for producing safe food.

Impact

The NOVASOIL knowledge hub collects and exchanges information and knowledge to boost the development and improvement of the existing business models related to soil health. In addition, the NOVASOIL knowledge hub will support the creation of new business models related to improving soil health.

Problem and solutions

The opportunities and gaps of new incentives are crucial to the redirection of financial streams and policy support measures for provision of innovative soil health technologies for producing safe food.

Short term investments in soil health can deliver long term results in food security and value chain. Farmers and land managers can face barriers to change practices, such as perceived risk, access to finance or initial costs.

Short term investments that share risks and costs or provide innovative finance options would help overcome those barriers, leading to long term returns.

Reviews of successful farmer-owned urban areas businesses, farmer, and forestry linkages point to the importance of new incentives development for: 1- market linkages for healthy soil new value chain development of safety food and services, 2- internal and bridging innovative ways of blending finance streams and policy measures, and 3- creating a soil health business models to reduce production costs and costs as a result of using a differentiated approach in food production systems.

Build a hub of knowledge, surveying, structuring, and connecting existing knowledge of existing incentives regarding investment opportunities at farm level of implementing different soil health business models.

Screening of the new incentives' alternatives will be made through cooperative research with end-users in WP5, based on the hypothesis that new soil health business models and/ or a significantly reducing their investment cost will allow experimentation to enable different kinds of farmers to be more innovative and novel opportunities for developing and diversifying income for land managers.

Figure 10. NOVASOIL DHK About us page

In addition, the About page has three important sub-menus – partners, frequently asked questions, and contact us.

3.2.1 Partners

The partner page presents all NOVASOIL partners. The page will be developed further with information about partners. It will include categories of the partners and a short partners' introduction.

The main group partners will be as follows:

- NOVASOIL partners
- Case Studies
- Sister projects
- Other partners

3.2.2 Frequently Asked Questions

The frequently asked question page will consist of the selection of the most frequent questions and provided short answers. If it is needed more information, there will be possibility to contact the team through the link to the contact form on the bottom of the FAQ page.

3.2.3 Contact us

The contact page will give information about the alternative channels for communication such as address, mail, and telephone.

Then the users will find a contact form through which they would contact the NOVASOIL team (fig. 11). Through this channel of communication, the NOVASOIL team will ensure a support in all NOVASOIL partners' languages.

Send us a message

Have a question, comment, or inquiry? We would love to hear from you! Send us a message using the form below, and our team will get back to you as soon as possible.

NAME COUNTRY

PHONE EMAIL

SUBJECT

MESSAGE

Send Message

Figure 11. NOVASOIL DHK message form

3.3 Soil health business models

This page will present all result of WP 1, WP 2, WP 3 related to the soil health business models. Also, there will be collected information from other projects and other sources.

The page will consist of two sub-pages: libraries and news.

3.4 Soil health practices

This page will present all result of WP 1 and WP 2 related to the soil health practices. Also, there will be collected information from other projects and other sources.

The page will consist of two sub-pages: libraries and news.

3.5 Soil health policies

This page will present all result of WP 4 related to the soil health policies. Also, there will be collected information from other projects and other sources.

The page will consist of two sub-pages: libraries and news.

3.6 Soil health projects

This page will present all result of NOVASOIL, and other EU projects related to the soil health. Also, there will be collected information from other sources.

The page will consist of two sub-pages: libraries and news.

3.7 Forum

The NOVASOIL DHK forum will be main tool which to ensure knowledge exchange between the partners and the other end users (fig. 12).

Figure 12. NOVASOIL DHK Forum page

The forum topics will be divided into the following groups:

- Soil health business models;
- Soil health practices;
- Soil health policies;
- Soil health projects;
- Incentives related to the soil health.

The NOVASOIL project team will ensure administrator and/or moderator who will check the posts before the post publication.

3.7 Log in area

The log in area includes username and password (fig. 13).

Figure 13. Log in page

In terms of registration, the user should complete information about:

- Names
- Age group: 18-29; 30-39; 40-49; 50-59; 60-69; +70;
- Gender: female; male; no binary; I prefer not to answer;
- User: farmer; policy maker; researcher; industry and supply chain actors; NGOs and civil society; landowners; consumers; other – specify.
- Country:
- e-mail
- password and re-enter the password.

The hub suggests two levels of registration – basic and premium users. The basic users are all registered users that are external for the hub and could not read projects documents with confidential status.

The premium users are those who have access to the non-public NOVASOIL project's documents. The premium users will be NOVASOIL partners, sister projects' partners, etc.

4 Conclusions

Deliverable 3.2 presents the preliminary version of the NOVASOIL knowledge hub. It is presented the adopted approach for selection of features on the hub which will improve customer experience and attract new users.

The functionality is described based on the four modules: dynamic, publishing, product, and communication. In addition, it is presented the design of the hub.

This deliverable sets the foundation for D 3.5 Report on final version of the knowledge hub for soil health business models due in M19.

Resources

1. Clickable demo version of the NOVASOIL hub is available at:
<https://novasoil.agma.studio/>

Acknowledgment

Annexes

Annex 1

Slides presented on plenary meeting in Sevilla related to the NOVASOIL knowledge hub and deliverable D3.2

WP 3 next steps

Dimitre Nikolov, Krasimir Kostenarov, Ekatherina Tzvetanova-Georgieva, Ivan Boevsky, Martin Banov
NBU, Bulgaria

▼ Final report
▼ Preliminary report

WP 3 Tasks and Deliverables

WP 3 – tasks 3.2 and 3.3 – Deliverables till M18

- D 3.2**
M 12 Preliminary version of the knowledge hub for soil health business models
- D 3.3**
M 16 Preliminary version of tools for analysis of the soil health business models
- D 3.4**
M 18 Report on new incentives soil health business models

WP 3 – T3.2 Identification of new incentives soil health business models (M8 –M16)

D 3.2 Preliminary version of the knowledge hub for soil health business models

- Build a hub of knowledge, surveying, structuring, and connecting existing knowledge of existing incentives regarding investment opportunities at farm level of implementing different soil health business models.
- Task 3.2 will build a hub of knowledge and for providing recommendations for connecting existing and new knowledge. This hub is about incentives for redirection of financial streams and policy support measures for provision of innovative soil health technologies for producing safe food.

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge – content

- Form of the provided information:
 - ✓ List of selected news.
 - ✓ Learning Modules
 - ✓ Resource books
 - ✓ Factsheets
 - ✓ Podcasts
 - ✓ Videos
- Presentation of partners in a list with logo, name, short text and link.
- Sample of selected partners on home page. News / events
- Sample of selected events on home page. Contacts
- Company contact information and address.
- Map with the location of the company's office.

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge – Site features

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge – Site features

04

-
- Navigation bar in the header of the site (Main menu).
 - Navigation bar in the final part of the site (Footer).
 - Social sharing buttons.
 - Ability to set the activity period of a certain event. Outside of the specified period the event is not displayed in the hub.
 - Form for inquiry and feedback: Name, e-mail, Telephone, Inquiry, Tick for consent to GDPR.
 - Information pages (success / failure) after sending the request.

Annex 2

Minutes

Meeting held on 30 August 2023

List of participants

Prof. D. Nikolov, assist. prof. E. Tzvetanova-Georgieva, Francisco Jose Blanco Velazquez, and Fernando Alonso Martin.

Agenda

Discussion on knowledge hub under T3.2.

Notes - Knowledge hub

The design of the knowledge hub will be in line with the project design – color palette, fonts, and so on.

The hub will include some of the information uploaded on the project site. The process of information synchronization should be determined.

The hub should be fed up with information. We should include information from the sister projects.

Francisco suggested organizing a meeting with the NOVASOIL project officer to involve other projects to use and feed the hub. The meetings will be at the beginning of October 2023. The owner of the hub will be a contact from NBU. The sources could be: other initiatives; Prepsoil project; information related to carbon credits.

It is good to try to provide information about different land usage. Also, to make collaboration for semiautomated toolbox.

Annex 3

Slides presented on plenary meeting in Munich related to the NOVASOIL knowledge hub and deliverable D3.2

WP 3 T3.2 KNOWLEDGE HUB

Dimitre Nikolov, Krasimir Kostenarov, Ekatherina Tzvetanova-Georgieva, Ivan Boevsky, Martin Banov, Kristina Todorova
NBU, Bulgaria

WP 3 – T3.2 Identification of new incentives soil health business models (M8 –M16)

D 3.2 Preliminary version of the knowledge hub for soil health business models

- Build a hub of knowledge, surveying, structuring, and connecting existing knowledge of existing incentives regarding investment opportunities at farm level of implementing different soil health business models.
- Task 3.2 will build a hub of knowledge and for providing recommendations for connecting existing and new knowledge. This hub is about incentives for redirection of financial streams and policy support measures for provision of innovative soil health technologies for producing safe food.

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge – content

- Form of the provided information:
 - ✓ List of selected news.
 - ✓ Learning Modules
 - ✓ Resource books
 - ✓ Factsheets
 - ✓ Podcasts
 - ✓ Videos
- Presentation of partners in a list with logo, name, short text and link.
- Sample of selected partners on home page. News / events
- Sample of selected events on home page. Contacts
- Company contact information and address.
- Map with the location of the company's office.

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge – Site features

01 Dynamic module
 For publishing pages: About Us, Products, Partners, etc. Ability to associate dynamic modules (Products, News, Contacts...) to a specific page. Frequently Asked Questions A dynamic module for publishing frequently asked questions and answers to them.

02 Product module
 For display all questions in a chronological list. When clicking on a specific question, outputs the corresponding answer.

03 Publishing module
 For ability to associate a list of questions with dynamic page and product modules. Partners Dynamic partner publishing module.

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge – Site features

- Navigation bar in the header of the site (Main menu).
- Navigation bar in the final part of the site (Footer).
- Social sharing buttons.
- Ability to set the activity period of a certain event. Outside of the specified period the event is not displayed in the hub.
- Form for inquiry and feedback: Name, e-mail, Telephone, Inquiry, Tick for consent to GDPR.
- Information pages (success / failure) after sending the request.

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge mock-up Homepage

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge mock -up Homepage

Comprehensive Knowledge Base

Our platform provides users with access to a comprehensive knowledge base that includes information on crop cultivation, soil health, pest management, organic farming, and much more.

Expert Advice and Support

We understand that agriculture can present unique challenges and complexities. That's why NOVASOIL provides a platform where users can seek advice and support from experts in the field.

Interactive Forums and Discussions

Our platform provides users with access to a comprehensive knowledge base that includes information on crop cultivation, soil health, pest management, organic farming, and much more.

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge mock -up Homepage

NOVASOIL PROJECT

At Novasoi, we believe in the power of technology and sustainability to drive positive change in farming practices. Through extensive research, collaboration, and advanced technology solutions, we are working towards creating a more efficient, resourceful, and eco-friendly agricultural ecosystem. Our project focuses on developing cutting-edge techniques, such as precision farming, smart irrigation systems, and data analytics, to optimize crop production while minimizing environmental impact.

[Discover more](#)

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge mock -up Homepage

Latest news

We invite you to join us on this journey towards a future where soil health is of paramount importance. Follow Novasoi for the latest updates on our research, partnerships, and initiatives, and discover how innovative business models can pave the way for a more sustainable and resilient world.

TUM

October 16, 2023 • No Comments

Zernrieku saclima

October 16, 2023 • No Comments

METK

October 16, 2023 • No Comments

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WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge mock -up Homepage

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WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge mock -up Partners

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10109208

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge mock -up Forum

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101019268

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge mock -up News

Funded by the European Union
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101019268

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge mock -up FAQ

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101019268

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge mock -up Contacts

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under grant agreement N°
101019268

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge mock -up Login

ABOUT PARTNERS PRODUCTS FORUM NEWS FAQ CONTACT US LOG IN

[Log in](#)
[Register](#)

USERNAME

PASSWORD

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101019268

WP 3 – T3.2 Hub of knowledge mock -up Feeding up the hub – Bulgaria

N°	Name	Short description	Link	Category in Library
1	National Program for Traditional and Regional Products 2022 - 2032	The document presents several key measures for the potential of local and regional products in increasing local economy and local communities. The	pdf	Policies
2	CAP Strategic Plan in BG 2023-2027	Main strategic document of the EU in support of agricultural development, whose main aim is to support farmers and to ensure Europe's food security.	pdf	Policies
3	Agriculture as part of the EU Recovery and Resilience	A short guiding document from the Ministry of Agriculture in BG on what are the main mechanisms for encouraging environmental transition of	pdf	Incentives
4	Practical guideline for implementing GAEC in BG 2023	A short guiding document from the Ministry of Agriculture in BG regarding several main standards, in keeping the agricultural land in good ecological	pdf	Incentives
5	EU Soil Strategy for 2030	EU strategic document on achieving good soil health, containing medium-term objectives by 2030 and long term objectives by 2050. The document provides good explanation on healthy soil. A connection is made between soil health and other strategic topics like circular economy, zero pollution, climate adaptations, etc.	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0699	Soil Health

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Thank you
For further information
<https://novasoil-project.eu>

